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The Influence of Worker's Trust and Motivation on Enterprises Performance

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ABSTRACT

The primary goal of this academic study was to determine the factors that influence worker motivation in the enterprise. The following research questions guided the study: (i) What are the new strategies that are capable of motivating workers in the enterprises? (ii) How does motivation affect worker's performance? (iii) What is the way forward for utilizing these new strategies effectively? A primary data research plan was adopted, focusing majorly on enterprises.

The populations for the study were workers across enterprises in Nigeria, considering her as one of the largest economies in Africa. The study population comprised a total of 356 respondents in which 400 was the initial target and comprises of workers from several enterprises. A sample size of 356 respondents was obtained using a stratified random selection procedure. The data assembly tool was standardizing online questionnaire developed by the scholar, explicitly for this study. It was subjected to comprehensive pretesting proceeding to execution. A set of quantitative empirical method was adopted to test the hypothesis which predicted motivation of workers in an enterprise positively influence enterprises performance. (1) used the Statistical Package for Social Scientists (SPSS) to calculate the correlations between the variables.

The study's main findings were that the relationship between independent variables (perceived job satisfaction, perceived training, and development) and trust in the enterprises was positive and significant except perceived job appraisal which was showing a negative relationship with trust in the enterprises. Promotion, compensation, fringe benefits, and the work are examples of extrinsic factors that motivate workers. Furthermore, the extrinsic factor is critical in persuading workers to strive for the set goals by quickly performing the required tasks at work. The research also discovered several intrinsic factors that influence worker's motivation. These included, among other things, worker accomplishments, commendation, the job itself, wage structure, commitment and promotion, the level of gratitude workers experience, and worker conception of their work. The study also discovered that worker motivation has an impact on worker performance in the enterprise,

which has a psychological impact as well as a beneficial role for enterprises. The study also discovered that motivated workers have the potential to create a positive work environment, which in turn increases worker loyalty to the enterprise and, as a result, increases productivity. The main results are that worker motivation is a highly delicate concept that is affected by a variety of factors. Few of these basic factors are unfamiliar in the sense that they emerge from within the organization and impose external discipline on the worker. The study also asserts that the concept of motivation as an individual or intrinsic characteristic in a person predisposes them to have a particular mindset towards their jobs.

According to the findings, enterprises should recognize and use external influences in their human resource management activities, particularly in strategic human resource management, to ensure that workforces are well motivated to be able to carry out their responsibilities effectively. Furthermore, enterprises should consider external factors such as encouraging worker participation in decision-making and creating opportunities for individual development, among other practices that can effectively support internal factors and assist in the development of high levels of worker motivation. Similarly, enterprises and government agencies should think about creating policies and activities that boost worker motivation. Finally, new research should focus on the topic of worker's motivation to aid in the understanding of this difficult concept.

Keywords

Motivation, Enterprises, Trust in Enterprises (TE)

Introduction

Various influences like capital, environmental and human resource influences impact on performance of enterprises. Of all these influences, human resource is taking the greatest influence on the performance of an enterprise. It is reasonable hence paramount that an enterprise requires to motivate its workers in order to accomplish its indicated objectives and goals (2). A perceptive of the factors that motivate workers and their proper application would have major effect on the enterprise's performance (3). Motivation has been described by many scholars as a decision-making process, through which goal-directed behavior is instigated, keyed up, directed, and maintained. Improving productivity is one big face up that has engaged the awareness of employers either private or public (4). Therefore, decision makers are experimenting for years with diverse strategies in an effort to effectively transmit, the motivation of workers to their performance (5).

Almost all enterprises aspire to be successful, even in today's highly competitive world. As a result, enterprises of all sizes and markets strive to retain the best personnel, recognizing their importance and influence on organizational performance (6). To overcome these problems, enterprises must foster a pleasant and strong relationship among their workforces and guide them toward task accomplishment (7). Enterprises should expand their tactics to compete in highly competitive marketplaces and improve their performance to attain their goals and objectives.

Only a few organizations, on the other hand, regard human capital as their most asset, capable of propelling them to success or, if poorly managed, to decline. The enterprise will not be successful if its personnel are dissatisfied with their jobs and are not driven to complete their obligations and achieve their objectives.

Humans have a variety of wants that constantly compete with one another. Different individuals have different combinations and strengths of wants, as some people are motivated by success while others are concerned about safety (6). Decision makers who are competent of understanding, anticipating, and controlling worker behavior should also be aware of what people want from their positions. As a result, it is critical for a leader to discover what truly motivates workers rather than relying on assumptions. Inquiring about a worker's feelings about a certain circumstance does not provide a whole picture of his demands, as the interpretation may be unreliable (8).

The business environment has experienced sizeable changes over the past years in terms of the quality and range of work. The dynamic nature of the work situation has required diametric ways of management approaches (9). Thus far a crucial and constant factor has been the ways in which decision maker motivate their workers to help accomplish not only the organizational goals but as well that of their own personal objectives (10). This cognitive factor stems from both the compound nature of the work environment as well as the broad array of workers employed within them. Humans are by nature not homogeneous entity. They possess collection of needs, aims, as well as dissent perceptions of what represent suitable rewards for impressive motivation (11). Therefore, motivating workers involves an in-depth understanding of the human nature, respective differences and perceptions of suitable rewards and incentives, as well as a sequence of extrinsic and intrinsic rewards (12). Regrettably majority of decision maker tend to accept, instead erroneously that they can decently motivate their workers by extending rewards such as higher remuneration, incentive, and paid vacations. (13) states that, in most cases there subsist an 'extrinsic incentive bias which is preserve by both managers and workers. As indicated by (14), this bias does not root from realism but are rather frozen in myths encompassing worker emotional state. Research has nonetheless demonstrated that such monetary incentives do not necessarily motivate workers and may in certain conditions become demotivates. Also, (15) maintains that monetary reward 'motivates solitary to a point; that is, when compensation isn't higher enough or is considered to be unjust, it's a demotivate.

(6) argue that every enterprise desires to thrive as much as present-day situation is very competitive. Enterprise regardless of name, goodwill, and marketplace endeavor to keep the best workers, adjudging their essential role and impact on enterprises strength. In order to subdue difficult tasks, enterprise should give room for a resilient and supportive link with its workers, shaping them in direction of job fulfillment and ascertain they have work contentment (1). Enterprises evolve techniques to compete in extremely competitive markets and to increase their efficiency to achieve their aims and objectives. Even so, only a few enterprises consider human capital to be their most valuable asset, capable of propelling them to success or, if poorly managed, leading to organizational failure and excessive staff turnover (16).

Theoretical Background

The hierarchy of needs hypothesis was proposed by Abraham Maslow. Maslow stated that there is a hierarchy of five major wants within every personality and before moving on to the next higher level of need, each degree of need must be met (4). The following are the five needs proposed by Maslow:

Physiological Needs

According to Abraham Maslow's theory, only a small percentage of the population achieves self-actualization. The enterprise can address the needs of its workers in several ways. In the long run, a person's wage may be able to meet physiological needs, but it's also important to remember that money can also be used to achieve other desires such as safety and esteem.

Safety Needs

It is inferred that giving substantial benefits, such as health insurance and company-sponsored retirement plans, as well as a sense of job security, will assist in meeting safety conditions.

Love and Sense of Belonging

Refers to social needs that can be satisfied by creating a friendly atmosphere and providing a work environment that promotes collaboration and communication picnics and other social gatherings, for example, may be advantageous if most workers are motivated primarily by social needs.

Self Esteem

Refers to a person's need to be respected and valued by others, which can be met by giving them opportunities for advancement at work, recognizing their successes verbally or through more formal incentive systems, and giving them job titles.

Self-Actualization

Refers to a person's full potential and how they can achieve it. For example, if you want to be an ideal personality, you can meet that demand by offering opportunities for development and progress both on and off the job, as well as compelling and challenging work.

Literature Review

The main concern in any enterprise is worker performance; the average enterprise's growth is totally dependent on the attitude and dedication of workers to their responsibilities. The most important issue for an enterprise is to maximize its performance (15). The worker's performance is referred to as good enterprise performance. Worker performance that is satisfactory does not happen by accident; it is influenced by leadership standards, knowledge and skill, commitment, and performance appraisal. Our research aims to determine the impact of worker motivation on enterprise performance, as well as how motivation influences the relationship between performance appraisal and enterprise performance.

Workers' motivation is a notion that has attracted the interest of decision-makers and researchers alike (17). It is considered that no company could ever grow without its workforce. Workers are the most important factor in determining whether an enterprise can survive for a long time. Workers are highly motivated will have an impact on the enterprise's performance and will be more likely to achieve the enterprise's objectives and goals

(6). Early research on worker motivation focused mostly on the variables that contributed to it being achieved. On the other hand, little research has been done on its effect on the performance (13). Several studies on worker motivation have been conducted, although they are primarily based on western enterprises, with relatively few studies on motivation conducted in African organizations/enterprises, let alone Nigeria. This creates a gap that needs to be addressed with extensive research, given that workers in varied contexts and from distinct cultures cannot be motivated by the same factors. Managers have had a significant difficulty in identifying how to obtain the highest level of motivation for their personnel, which they believe would go a long way toward improving enterprise performance.

Research Methodology

The study aims and objectives are to define more factors that can contribute to motivation of workers in some enterprises which will invariably leads to organizational growth and development. We ran a survey to acquire primary data because the information needed for this study was not available in the form of secondary data. A questionnaire base investigation was conducted at various enterprises particularly in Nigeria to authenticate the study model.

This research adopted quantitative empirical research to test the hypothesis which predicted that the motivation of workers in an organization positively influenced organization performance. Also, the degree of trust in the four variables moderates the role of trust as a moderator between work satisfaction, appraisals, training, and development. A questionnaire will also be utilized to investigate the relationship between trust in the enterprises, perceived job satisfaction, perceived job appraisal, and perceived training and development. Nigeria was chosen because I understand Nigeria terrain of manufacturing and public companies and Nigeria been one of the highest employers of labor in Africa economy.

Also, the sampling location is a major hearth of businesses and economic location in Africa. The questionnaire was distributed among the workers in public and manufacturing companies across the nation and it was based on systematic sampling through which every worker participated. The survey was carried out with the help of a standard online questionnaire that had undergone extensive pre-testing before implementation. This was proofread by two academic scholars in University of Ibadan to ascertain the suitability of the questions and measurement in the questionnaire.

After that, a pilot study was conducted with 50 respondents to show how the responses correspond to the research objectives and questions. After the data collection period, a final analysis was conducted using 356 responses out of a total of 400 which is equivalent to 89% responses. The research adopted structural equation modeling by using LISREL to 8.7 to analyze the data. Hayes (2013) built an annex of SPSS known as macro was used to test the full hypothesis. The following questions will suggest a method for achieving the study's goal and objective:

1. What are the new strategies that are capable motivating workers?
2. How does it affect worker's performance?

3. What is the way forward of using new strategies effectively

The proposed model

Figure 1: Worker's motivation and organization performance

This model is intended to assess an enterprise's success based on three independent variables: perceived job satisfaction, perceived job appraisal, and perceived training and development. With this approach, we can connect the relationship between these independent variables to determine enterprise performance with trust in the enterprises functioning as a mediator between them. These variables were also chosen for their flexibility and applicability in assessing the performance of enterprises.

Perceived Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction is defined by (18) as a pleasant or positive emotional state related to the evaluation of a specific duty or work content. It was created because of a variability of behavior and work situation features, as well as a prelude to the ultimate output. Workers who are more satisfied with their jobs are less likely to be absent, less likely to leave, more productive, more likely to be loyal to the organization, and more likely to be retained by them (1).

Perceived Job Appraisal

Performance appraisals are necessary for efficient assessment and management of workers in an enterprise. Since perceptions of work influence worker's opinion and mental attitude towards specific behavior, it could be predictable that the workers of an enterprises might view different sentiments about the performance appraisal strategy in the enterprise. The human resource method can transform to more impelling by possessing a sound and accurate appraisal scheme used for evaluating performances of workers (19).

Perceived Training and Development

In the ever-changing and competitive modern market, training has become a buzzword. Personnel distinguishes a great organization from a bad one. Enterprises that invest in effective human resource training and development to achieve both immediate and long-term goals. Training and development is primary at all worker levels, due to the rationality that skills dilapidated and become outdated over a period of time and has to be revived (6).

Trust in the Enterprises

Trust can be defined as one's perception of others, as well as their decision to act based on communication, conduct, and their own preferences. If an enterprise seeks to succeed and thrive, trust is essential, and it should be always maintained to ensure the enterprise's survival and enhance worker motivation. This can have social and interpersonal consequences, as well as a bearing on company operations both inside and beyond the enterprise (20). A potential worker frequently seek information from within the organization to determine if an organization can be relied on (8).

Enterprises Performance

Enterprise performance assessment is a core organizational tool for enterprises to use strategic management, as well as a fundamental means of self-supervision and self-restraint (21).

The assessment of relevant enterprise activity records over a given period in front of the management level of enterprises is the quantitative performance appraisal method of enterprises. Efficient performance assessment benefits enterprise decision makers and other stakeholders by allowing them to gain a comprehensive understanding of the enterprise's operational modalities and development goals, as well as for company to establish a perfect, impressive discipline and motivator techniques.

Hypothesis

H1: Enterprise performance and trust in the enterprise have a good and direct relationship. Trust is a key component in establishing a successful relationship between perceived job satisfaction, perceived job appraisal, and perceived training and development. Trust has been playing as a catalyst for workers and management relationship to last long.

H2: Perceived job satisfaction and trust in enterprises have a favorable relationship that influences enterprise performance.

Workers' trust in their enterprises will motivate them to contribute to the enterprise's performance. Perceived job satisfaction refers to workers' perceptions of how contented they are in their enterprises, particularly their perceptions of comfort and security, which can lead to unproductive behavior.

H3: Job appraisal was found to be negatively related to trust in the ability of an enterprise to enhance its performance. Perceived job appraisal examines how sub-constructs of appraisal, such as proportional advantage and extrinsic incentive, influence enterprise performance.

H4: Perceived training and development is positively related to trust in the enterprises to aid enterprises performance. It stressed the importance of a positive working environment and worker training to improve an

enterprise's performance. Findings reveal that perceived training and development of workers in an enterprise defines enterprise performance, and that perceived training and development, as well as cultural consequences, affect the level of enterprise performance.

Table 1: Demographic information of the respondents

	Measures	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	198	51.6
	Female	158	44.4
Age	(Below 18)	39	8.1
	(18-30)	137	48.5
	(31-45)	135	36.9
	(45 and above)	45	6.5
Education Status	Secondary school	48	19.8
	BSc	134	45.6
	Masters	133	29.1
	Ph.D.	41	5.5
Marital Status	Married	135	42.9
	Single	208	53.7
	Divorce	13	3.4
Income	Less than \$100	57	17.0
	\$200 - \$499	183	59.1
	\$500 – above	116	23.9

Test for Reliability of Independent Variables

The details used for reliability test are predicted to be tested and accurate; it is a crucial procedure to be certain that the details that are utilized for representing the independent variables are valid, before proceeding deep in analysis for measuring the research hypotheses. Therefore, if the general details of Cronbach's Alpha are above 0.7 and it means that the details are reliable and can be used for future analysis in order to analyze the research hypotheses.

Perceived job satisfaction is the first independent variable in this proposed research model, and it was measured through three items using the total items Cronbach's Alpha = 0.914.

The second independent variable of this survey was perceived job appraisal. It was calculated through four items using the total items Cronbach's Alpha = 0.803. And the third independent variable of this study was perceived training and development. As well, it was calculated using four items, the total items Cronbach's

Alpha = 0.886, since the Cronbach's Alpha is above 0.7, thus, all the three items representing independent variable are all reliable and can be utilize in any statistical analysis or investigate research hypotheses.

Test for Reliability and Validity of Mediator Variable

The mediator variable (trust in the enterprises) of this proposed model is the one influencing the relationship between the dependent variable and three predictor's independent variables. Before analyzing and studying the mediation effect as proposed in the model, we carried out reliability test for the items that are representing the mediator and ensure that the Cronbach's Alpha is above 0.7 which shows that the items utilized for representing the moderator are reliable. The moderator effect which is trust in the enterprises, acted as a bridging gap between them and the relationship was tested consequently with the reliability of the items that stand for independent variables which was measured through the items using the Cronbach's Alpha = 0.904.

Measurement of Variables/ Estimation approach

Measurement items were adapted from prior studies with modest terminology and phrase adjustments to meet the current study. The measures for measuring perceived job satisfaction were adapted from a study of (8) with three items such as "the monetary reward/salary structure has an effect on my level of motivation" ; perceived job appraisal (19) and the measurement items were four with a question like "I am more motivated to do my job when I feel I am recognized and appreciated for my contribution to the enterprises"; perceived training and development was adapted from (16) with four measurement items such as "the level of empowerment and employee liberty at my enterprises has an impact on my motivation" while trust in the enterprises was adapted from (8) with four items like "I have trust in the organization I work with" and lastly, enterprises performance was adapted from (19) with four questions like "the sense of belonging workers have in my enterprises has direct impact on organization performance".

The responses were evaluated on a 5-point Likert scale, where 1 signifying strong agreement, 3 denoting neutrality, and 5 denoting extreme disagree. All the measurement items for the variables together with their sources and other evident items used in this study can be recovered in the appendix attached.

To analyze the latent variables within their causal structure, we adopted structural equation modeling (SEM) using LISREL software. SEM concept was adopted considering been an important simplification of preceding statistical methods through the valuable advantage for the fact that it has the quality to test explanatory effects between the variables, hierarchical regression, measurement, and structural models can be run at the same time thus it brings the postulation that variables are measured absolutely. Moreover, SEM tolerates numerous indicators of dormant variables which remain a more applicable representation of the variables under study.

The table below indicates the respective measurements utilized to measure the constructs.

Table 2: Measurement Items

CONSTRUCT	ITEMS	REFERENCES
Enterprises performance	I believe the level of employee motivation in my enterprises has a	(19)

	<p>direct impact on organizational growth.</p> <p>The level of employee motivation at my current place of work has a direct impact on organization performance.</p> <p>The sense of belonging workers has in my enterprises has direct impact on organization performance.</p> <p>The degree of motivation of workers in the organization has a direct effect on the levels of organization performance.</p>	
Trust in the enterprises	<p>I have trust in the organization I work with.</p> <p>I am assured of my job security in the enterprises.</p> <p>I can dedicate the rest of my working career to my enterprises.</p> <p>I do not need to push before my benefits are paid in my enterprises</p>	(8)
Perceived job satisfaction in an enterprises	<p>The monetary reward/salary structure has an effect on my level of motivation.</p> <p>I am satisfied with the style of leadership in my enterprises</p> <p>The quality of work condition in my enterprises satisfy me as a worker</p>	(8)
Perceived job appraisal	<p>I am more motivated to do my job when I feel I am recognized and appreciated for my contribution to the enterprises.</p> <p>I am more motivated to perform my duty when I feel there is fairness of treatment at the workplace.</p>	(19)

	<p>I am more motivated whenever I am promoted in my enterprises.</p> <p>I always derived joy whenever my enterprises appreciate my efforts</p>	
Perceived training and development	<p>The level of empowerment and employee liberty at my enterprises has an impact on my motivation.</p> <p>I get the required training and development in my enterprises.</p> <p>What I acquired from training and development in my enterprises is of great value to my career.</p> <p>Training and development is of great value to our enterprises development.</p>	(16)

Results

Step 1

Structured equation modeling (SEM) was used to analyze the data, and LISREL 8.70 was used to examine and evaluate the structural equation model. In this study, exploratory factor analysis was used to divide the proportional reduction of items. The data's reliability was tested using the reliability test. Researchers used an incredible tool that combined regression analysis, confirmatory factor analysis, and a structural model to access the measurement model (22). Cronbach's alpha, composite reliability, and average variance extracted (AVE) threshold levels were 0.7, 0.7, and 0.5, respectively (7). The composite reliability and Cronbach's alpha values were both above 0.7, while the AVE values for all constructs were all above 0.5, showing a high level of convergent validity.

According to (7), another technique to determine discriminating validity is to look at the relationship between correlation, constructs, and the square root of the AVE of all constructs. When the square root of AVE exceeds the correlation between constructs, substantial discriminating validity is indicated. The above figure depicts the results of the data validity analysis.

Table 3: Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA)

Constructs			Factor loading	Cronbach Alpha	AVE	CR
Perceived job satisfaction	job	PJS1	0.828	0.913	0.721	0.881
		PJS2	0.856			
		PJS3	0.899			
Perceived job appraisal	job	PJA1	0.761	0.813	0.508	0.802
		PJA2	0.652			
		PJA3	0.589			
		PJA4	0.861			
Perceived training and development		PTD1	0.785	0.876	0.657	0.882
		PTD2	0.805			
		PTD3	0.780			
		PTD4	0.856			
Trust in the enterprises	the	TE1	0.852	0.914	0.695	0.897
		TE2	0.844			
		TE3	0.847			
		TE4	0,766			

Extraction Method: Maximum Likelihood. Rotation Method: Prom ax with Kaiser Normalization

Table 4: Means, standard deviations, correlations, and AVE Square-root

Constructs	Mean	(SD)	PJS	PJA	PTD	TE	EP
PJS	1.78	(0.747)	0.855				
PJA	1.65	(0.487)	0.331	0.712			
PTD	1.54	(0.540)	0.492	0.458	0.804		
TM	1.73	(0.722)	0.656	0.230	0.435	0.828	
A	1.52	(0.578)	0.373	0.309	0.369	0.402	0.789

Note. N=356. All correlations are significant at $p < 0.001$. Values on the diagonal represent average variance extracted (AVE)

Step 2

SEM is a multidisciplinary research technique that has evolved into one of the most important systems used by researchers to verify their findings (4). To measure model fitness, researchers must look at markers such

the root mean square root error of approximation (RMSEA), Chi – square, adjusted goodness of fit index (AGFI), goodness of fit index (GFI), Tucker – Lewis's index (TLI), and comparative fit index (CFI). Depending on the sample size, the chi-square value for model goodness must not be less than 2.0 and not more than 5.0, according to prior studies (23).

The RMSEA value should be less than 0.10, with a maximum limit of 0.7 and a minimum of 0.08 (7). According to the GFI and AGFI indexes, they can have values larger than 0.90 and 0.80, respectively. Several researchers have demonstrated that the NFI, IFI, and CFI indices can have values greater than 0.85. (7). The SEM approach was replicated in this work using LISREL 8.70, and confirmatory analysis was utilized to measure model goodness of fit using indices. As indicated in the table above, the study's indices demonstrated enough goodness of fit for measurement and structural model, with all chi-squares, RMSEA, IFI, NFI, TLI, CFI, AGFI, and GFI computations falling within ample scope.

Table 5: Measurement Model

Fit indices	χ^2/df	RMSEA	GFI	AGFI	CFI	NFI	NNFI	IFI
Recommended value	<3	<0.08	>0.90	>0.80	>0.90	>0.90	>0.90	>0.90
Value in this study	1.634	0.042	0.93	0.92	0.98	0.99	0.96	0.98

Table 6: Structural Model

Fit indices	χ^2/df	RMSEA	GFI	AGFI	CFI	NFI	NNFI	IFI
Recommended value	<3	<0.08	>0.90	>0.80	>0.90	>0.90	>0.90	>0.90
Value in this study	1.747	0.047	0.94	0.92	0.98	0.97	0.97	0.98

The reliability test findings convincingly suggest that the correlations among the exogenous variables have no effect on the validity of our outcomes. The next phase was to focus on the structural model after gaining confidence in the measurement's accuracy. The goodness of fit measures for the structural model are satisfactory ($\chi^2/df = 1.746$; GFI =.93; AGFI =.91; TLI =.82; RMSEA=.046).

Finally, we looked at multicollinearity by looking at the amplitude of bivariate correlations between exogenous variables (see Table 4). In addition, the results of the stability tests revealed that multicollinearity was not an issue in our study.

Hypotheses Testing

Subsequent step is to test the hypothesis relationship. As showed by the results, the significant path coefficient appears to support the proposed model. With the help of H1, Job satisfaction and trust in the enterprise's performance have a significant and positive relationship, according to our findings ($\beta = 0.64$; $p < .001$).

Nevertheless, perceived job appraisal was found to be negatively associated with trust in the enterprises whose path was illustrated as ($\beta = -0.07$; $p > 0.05$) and was established not significant indicating an intense negative

relationship between job appraisal as well as trust in the enterprises. Invariably, despite the perceived job appraisal in the enterprises, workers may not be comfortable working towards the enterprise's development probably because of other factors not related with enterprises performance. In any case, the structural connection from perceived training and development and trust in the enterprises is positive and significant ($\beta = .18$; $p < .01$), therefore mainly leading to enterprises performance and supporting H3. Furthermore, trust in the enterprises was established to act a mediating part between the independent variables (perceived job satisfaction, perceived job appraisal, perceived training, and development) and the dependent variable in which case H4 had a positive value ($\beta = 0.43$; $p < .001$).

For all datasets, the design of results reconciled with our hypotheses excluding the connection between job appraisal as well as enterprises performance because of its negative relationship. Thus, all hypothesized relationships were substantiated in the samples, which further accent the strength of our results.

Discussion

The original motive of this investigation was to examine the influence of enterprises performance by putting into consideration the perceived job satisfaction influence, perceived job appraisal and perceived training and development of workers in an enterprise.

The motivation of workers is a crucial motivating force aimed at advance change and revolution of the enterprise's development. Thus, encouraging workers in an enterprise by given them the required motivational tools remains crucial to fundamental transformations in the enterprises which can inspire the human resources field at a profound state to accomplish thriving and justifiable improvement in an enterprise.

Figure 2: Path diagram (** $p < 0.05$; *** $p < 0.01$)

Workers' motivation in the workplace can be enhanced by giving modern motivational factors that encourage workers to give their best to the organization's success and development. Scholars, decision-makers, and North American Academic Research, 5(4) | April 2022 | <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6502680> Monthly Journal by TWASP, USA | 183

professionals should focus on developing motivating benefits and providing workers with realistic and suitable current motivating instruments to help enterprises achieve their developmental goals.

The findings show that reported job satisfaction and enterprise performance are both mediated by trust in the enterprise. This has a good and significant impact on the performance of enterprises. On the other hand, perceived job appraisal had a negative and non-significant impact on business performance. This is a result of the awareness that regardless of a worker's perceived performance appraisal, it does not guarantee the worker's mentality toward motivating them. The relationship between perceived training and development and enterprise performance has been demonstrated, promoting trust between the two variables.

This is the first study to look at how trust can be used to mediate the relationship between individual behavior (perceived job satisfaction, perceived job appraisal, and perceived training and development) and performance of the enterprise. The study also adds to the motivation literature by looking into the relationship between job satisfaction, job appraisal, and training and development, as well as workers' drive to improve the performance of their enterprises. Many scholars consider worker motivation to be one of the most fundamental problems in today's high-growth large enterprises (17). To improve enterprise performance, decision makers, managers, and business owners might use an incentive strategy to persuade potential workers to stay on the path of enterprise development rather than looking for work elsewhere, which could harm the enterprise's performance. This would help the companies grow in a sustainable and profitable manner.

Limitations

Aspiring scholars could also include this study in their literature reviews and conduct additional research in the direction that this study has investigated to improve the current study and the overall understanding of worker motivation. Due to a lack of understanding among workers in the enterprises, the study is severely undermined. As a result, scholars can delve further into other psychological terrain to motivate personnel in small and medium enterprises.

Conclusion

For years, previous motivation research has mostly concentrated on regular motivation principles. Furthermore, the conclusions are complicated by the variability of the theoretical models used in various motivation research. Also, workers respond differently to their psychological demands, which can motivate them in ways that are different from the ones that decision-makers rely on all the time. All these issues have added to the difficulty of identifying study findings and formulating significant conclusions. In addition, the following conclusions were reached based on the outcomes of this study.

The findings show that perceived job satisfaction has a considerable and positive impact on business performance, whereas perceived job appraisal has a strong negative and extremely minor impact. Furthermore,

the findings revealed a positive association between perceived training and development and enterprise performance. This suggests that increasing motivation of workers has a favorable effect on the enterprise. Many workers were under-motivated because there was no perceived job appraisal after good performance in an enterprise and no positive response after performance of duties in terms of training and development, resulting in a negative outcome. As a result, the enterprises must devise a strategy to improve on training and development of workers in an enterprise so that their workers are satisfied and loyal, and the study's main objective, which was to determine whether workers are satisfied and loyal, will be met. Human resource management must be improved by enterprises since it has a significant impact on their overall performance.

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